

**MEANS OF DEPICTING NATURE IN THE WORKS OF
M.YU. LERMONTOV AND A.A. FET**

Аюров Timur Rustamovich

Senior Lecturer, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
named after Mukimiy, Uzbekistan, Kokand.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10690860>

ANNOTATION

Like any poet, Lermontov expressed in his works the era in which he lived; and the spirit of this era is reflection, doubt, deep thoughts about life without hope for the future. The consciousness of one's exclusivity in a world where only mediocrity is blissful again and again evokes a feeling of sad loneliness. This motif, persistent in Lermontov's lyrics, also sounds in works dedicated to nature.

In Lermontov's lyrics there is a constant appeal to nature, which helps to reveal the unity of the spiritual world of the lyrical hero and the natural world. The poet's lyrical hero, in his loneliness, is drawn to nature and knows how to see its beauty. Nature seems to emphasize the loneliness of the lyrical hero. A pine tree grows alone "in the wild north", dreaming of a distant palm tree; The giant cliff remains alone in the poem "The Cliff".

Key words: *Russian literature, national literature, M.Yu. Lermontov, A.A. Fet, work of art, lessons at school, phenomenon of national culture, national environment, lexicon Belinsky V.G., G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, OK. Bogomolov.*

The same dramas play out there as among people. A lonely old cliff, abandoned by a cloud, "cries softly." And how close to Lermontov's lyrical hero is the leaf, this eternal wanderer, torn from the branch, useless to anyone, not knowing sleep or peace. How characteristic is it that "he is ripe before his time." After all, this is how Lermontov will write about the whole generation, comparing it with the early fruits ("Soul"). Poems of this type are based on personification and can be called allegorical. Even the translation of Heine's poem sounds completely original: "In the wild north..." Lermontov very accurately uses the technique of animation. The technique of animation is not uncommon in poetry, but, according to the observations of researchers, Lermontov for the first time in Russian poetry began to draw comparisons from the natural world in relation to humans [1. p. 172].

Lermontov subtly senses the beauty of his native nature. It is not surprising that landscape sketches are an integral part of his lyrical works. In the lyrics of mature years, pictures of nature are, as it were, cleared of emotional verbal embellishments and exaggerations - everything in them is simple, truthful, accurate and economical. In his lyrics, "pure" landscape is almost

absent. He most often talks about what thoughts and feelings nature calls. “Yellowing cornfield”, “icy spring” running along the ravine, “silver lily of the valley” - all this calms the poet and relieves mental anxieties. Lermontov loves the earth: “We cannot love the earth more than the heavens.” He is all on earth and all earthly. And he acts like the hero of the poem “Confession,” who sees only earthly things in the heavenly, and is not afraid of either hell or “eternity”:

Lermontov glorifies the nature of his Fatherland: this is love for the country and nature and hatred for those people who are slaves of the autocracy [2. p. 37].

Contemplation of nature helps the poet understand that the highest expediency and beauty must triumph in human society. After all, man was not born for suffering alone? Otherwise, why did nature or the Creator endow him with a sense of justice, a desire for truth and a thirst for happiness? A yellowing cornfield, a forest, a gust of wind, a silver lily of the valley - all of these are not scattered and especially not isolated phenomena. These are the edges of whole being. Lermontov knew how to spiritualize, revive nature: a cliff, clouds, an oak leaf, a palm tree, a pine tree, friendly waves are endowed with human passions, they know the joy of meetings, the bitterness of separation, and insatiable sadness. By 1841, Lermontov's lyrics reached their peak. In the last year of his life, the poet created a number of works of amazing skill. Among them, a special place is occupied by “Motherland”, “Farewell, unwashed Russia”, “I go out alone on the road”. Nature here symbolizes the image of the Motherland. In the poem “I Go Out Alone on the Road,” the landscape occupies only five lines out of twenty. Moreover, this is a very unusual landscape that has symbolic meaning. The whole picture of the life of the lyrical hero is presented against a cosmic background and therefore takes on the appearance of a complex image-symbol, reminiscent of the painfully complex issues that Lermontov's contemporaries struggled to resolve:

I go out alone on the road;
Through the fog the flinty path shines;
The night is quiet. The desert listens to God
And star speaks to star.

The flint path is a figurative embodiment of the fate of the poet, who tried to find a response from his contemporaries, but remained unanswered, realizing complete loneliness in the desert desert. Flint reminds of blood, wounds,

suffering. But there should be no alienation and misunderstanding! After all, in the universe everything is connected to each other. Even star speaks to star... [3. p. 37]

In the poem “When the yellowing field is agitated...” to create a picture of ideal beauty, the poet uses emotional epithets: “sweet leaf”, “fragrant dew”, “mysterious saga”, “peaceful land”. All means are aimed at showing the poetry and at the same time the calming effect of nature on humans:

Then the anxiety of my soul is humbled,
Then the wrinkles on the forehead disperse, -
And I can comprehend happiness on earth,
And in the heavens I see God... [4. p. 85]

Nature in Lermontov's works has always been a symbol of freedom. In his poems and poems, he glorified the nature of the Caucasus. These were romantic sketches that amazed the reader with unusual colors. Lermontov shares his thoughts with us, talks about his joys and sorrows, delights and sorrows caused by certain events in his personal or public life [5. p. 52].

M.Yu. Lermontov affirms his love for Russian nature, for the Russian land cultivated by people's labor. Here you can trace the connection between the theme of nature and the theme of the Motherland. The theme of the Motherland runs through all of Lermontov's work. The embodiment of this theme in Lermontov's works is associated with the artistic method. Lermontov is a romantic, therefore, in addition to the specific image of Russia, a generalized symbolic image of the Motherland appears in his lyrics. Lermontov calls his love for his homeland “strange.” The “strangeness” lay in the poet's ambivalent attitude towards his Motherland. M.Yu. Lermontov condemns official official patriotism, and at the same time, “with joy unfamiliar to many,” the poet looks at the vast forests and fields, the steppes and rivers:

But I love - for what, I don't know myself -
Its steppes are coldly silent,
Its boundless forests sway... [4. p. 17]

M.Yu. Lermontov infinitely loved the Motherland, the Russian people, and subtly felt the beauty of Russian nature. It is not surprising that landscape sketches are an integral part of his lyrical and prose works. On the one hand,

pictures of nature in Lermontov's lyrics perform a service function: they either act as a background against which the action of the poem unfolds, or serve as a metaphor, comparison and help to reveal the image of the lyrical hero, to reveal certain shades of his experiences. This is manifested in such poems as "I go out alone on the road...", "Mountain Peaks", "Three Palms", and others. [6. p. 74].

On the other hand, the natural world has independence, and this world is disharmonious, split into earth and sky, below and above. Everything finite, transitory, and temporary is connected with the earth. The sky embodies eternity. Mountains act as a kind of connecting link between earth and sky. They are unshakable and not subject to destruction.

Bibliography:

1. Blagoy D. The world as beauty About "Evening Lights" by A. Fet. - M., 2005. – 42 p.
2. Belinsky V.G. Complete works. - M., 1834-1848
3. Grigoriev A. Essay. - St. Petersburg, 2006. – vol.1. - 85 s.
4. Golovanova T.B. Legacy of M.Yu. Lermontov in Soviet poetry. - M.: "Science" 2008. – 21 p.
5. Druzhinin V.B. Selected articles. – M., 1991. – 46 s.
6. Druzhinin A.V. Beautiful and eternal. - M., 2009. – 71 p.
7. Zolotussky I. "Gogol. Lermontov. Zhukovsky. Literary essays. - M., 2006. - 37 p.